

High Frequency Electromagnetic Induction Sensing for Non-Metallic Ordnances Detection

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Abstract—High frequency (>100 kHz) electromagnetic induction (HFEMI) sensing phenomena are investigated for non-metallic ordnances detection and discrimination. HFEMI responses are studied using numerical and experimental data. The numerical modeling is done via the method of auxiliary sources, and data are collected using a new HEMI system, that has been developed at our lab. The comparisons between modeled and actual data are illustrated for a non-metallic 105 mm projectile.

Index Terms—Electromagnetic induction; sensing; MAS, IED, Subsurface sensing.

I. INTRODUCTION

Intermediate electrically conducting (IEC) subsurface targets, such as homemade improvised advanced weapons, which use alternative materials for munitions structure components (e.g., casing, nose, fins), are not detectable with the current geophysical sensors used in the detection of unexploded ordnances (UXO) [1]. The detection of IEC subsurface targets gets more challenging in difficult sensing environments (e.g. high conductivity soils, saturated soils, low contrast soil-target environments). Therefore, in order to detect and segregate IEC hazardous subsurface targets from environment and metallic clutters new EMI sensing modalities needs to be developed.

In this work, we investigated EMI sensing phenomena from IEC targets using a full 3D EMI solver based on the Method of Auxiliary sources and a new broadband HFEMI system. The studies are done for a non-metallic 105mm projectile.

II. NUMERICAL MODELING

The method of auxiliary sources (MAS) is a numerical technique designed for solving various electromagnetic radiation and scattering problems. The MAS is robust, easy to

implement, and accurate, and has been used to investigate waveguide structures, antennas, scattering, electromagnetic wave propagation in complex media, etc [2]. It has also been employed successfully in the analysis of low-frequency electromagnetic induction scattering phenomena [3]-[6]. In the MAS, boundary value problems are solved numerically by representing the electromagnetic fields in each domain of the structure under investigation by a finite linear combination of analytical solutions of the relevant field equations, corresponding to sources situated at some distance away from the boundaries of each domain. The “auxiliary sources” producing these analytical solutions are chosen to be elementary dipoles/charges/currents located on fictitious auxiliary surface(s) that usually conform to the actual surface(s) of the structure. The method only requires points on the auxiliary and actual surfaces, so it is not necessary to resort to the detailed mesh structures required by, say, finite-element or boundary-element methods.

The two auxiliary surfaces are set up inside and outside the penetrable scattering object. The fields outside of the structure are considered to originate from a set of auxiliary sources placed inside the object, while the fields inside the object are taken to arise from a set of auxiliary sources placed outside. The interior and exterior fields thus constructed are required to obey Maxwell’s boundary conditions—the continuity of the tangential magnetic field and the jump condition for the normal magnetic field—at arrays of selected points on the physical surface(s) of the structure. This results in a matrix equation in which the amplitudes of the auxiliary sources are the unknowns. Once these amplitudes are found, the electromagnetic field—as well as any quantity related to it—can easily be computed throughout the computational space.

EMI scattering responses are usually expressed in terms of the induction number, a quantity inversely proportional to the

skin depth. It is well established that the electromagnetic field inside a conductor decays over distances of the order of the skin depth, and thus that the efficiency and accuracy of the MAS are reduced at high induction numbers due to singularities that appear in the scattering matrix. To overcome this problem, a combined MAS-thin skin approximation (MAS-TSA) [6] based on the divergence-free Maxwell equation for the magnetic field was developed and used to solve a variety of EMI problems related to land-based UXO detection and discrimination, from the magnetostatic regime up to 1 MHz. The TSA assumption, however, is found to break down when targets are placed in conducting media because satisfying the divergence-free equation is not sufficient to guarantee that all necessary boundary conditions for the electric and magnetic fields are obeyed. We have overcome this difficulty by employing the surface impedance boundary condition (SIBC) [7]. The combined MAS-SIBC approach is used to model wideband HFEMI field scattering for IEC targets.

III. FORMULATION OF HFEMI PROBLEM

Let us consider an IEC target is illuminated with a time-varying primary electromagnetic field originating from a transmitter coil (Figure 1).

Figure 1. A schematic diagram of EMI field scattering from an IEC target.

The computational region is divided into two parts: the volume outside the IEC target is referred to as Region 0 with free-space electromagnetic parameters; while Region 1 corresponds to the volume inside the IEC target with ϵ , σ , μ electromagnetic. The primary field induces eddy currents within the region 1, which in turn produce secondary (scattered) fields. The magnetic field inside each region can be expressed as

$$\mathbf{H}_\alpha(\vec{r}) = k_\alpha^2 \mathbf{\Pi}_\alpha^m(\mathbf{r}) + \nabla \nabla \cdot \mathbf{\Pi}_\alpha^m(\mathbf{r}), \quad (1)$$

where

$$\mathbf{\Pi}_\alpha^m(\mathbf{r}) = \sum_{n=1} \frac{1}{4\pi\mu_\alpha} \frac{\mathbf{P}_{\alpha,n}^o e^{-jk_\alpha |\mathbf{r}-\mathbf{r}_{\alpha,n}^o|}}{|\mathbf{r}-\mathbf{r}_{\alpha,n}^o|}. \quad (2)$$

Here $\mathbf{\Pi}_\alpha^m(\mathbf{r})$ is the fundamental solution of the Helmholtz equation, $k_\alpha = \sqrt{-j\omega\sigma_\alpha\mu_\alpha}$, $\alpha = 0,1$, $\mathbf{P}_{\alpha,n}^o$ is the n^{th} unknown magnetic dipole source coefficient placed on the auxiliary surfaces. The time dependence $e^{i\omega t}$ is assumed and suppressed in all subsequent discussions. These sources reside on an auxiliary surface slightly outside and approximately following the real surface. Each vector $\mathbf{P}_{\alpha,n}^{i,o}$ consists of two components approximately parallel to the real surface (equivalently, two crossed magnetic-current elements), or of one component for a cylindrically symmetric problem. We compute the total field inside each $\alpha = 0,1$ region by assuming that these sources radiate into an infinite homogeneous medium with the properties of the corresponding region.

The electromagnetic fields at each interface between the two regions are constrained by a set of boundary conditions. Specifically, the tangential component of the magnetic field and the normal component of the magnetic flux density must be continuous across real surface, i.e.:

$$\begin{aligned} [\tilde{\mathbf{n}} \times (\mathbf{H}_\alpha^{\text{tot}} - \mathbf{H}_{\alpha+1}^{\text{tot}})] &= \mathbf{0}, \\ \tilde{\mathbf{n}} \cdot (\mathbf{B}_\alpha^{\text{tot}} - \mathbf{B}_{\alpha+1}^{\text{tot}}) &= 0, \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

where $\tilde{\mathbf{n}}$ is a unit normal vector on the interface between the two regions. Enforcing (3) at selected collocation points on the real surface provides a matrix equation that is solved for the unknown coefficients $\{\mathbf{P}_{\alpha,n}^o\}$ and $\{\mathbf{P}_{\alpha,n}^i\}$. Once these are determined, we may readily compute the field at all points inside and outside the system see Figure 1 in both frequency and time domain for any transmitter configurations.

Figure 2. HFEMI system's experimental setup.

Figure 3. Modeled and measured wideband frequency-domain response of a non-metallic 105 mm projectiles placed a) vertically and b) horizontally. The measured in-phase and quadrature signals (open circles) agrees with modeled data up to 800 kHz. At frequencies above 800 kHz data show inconsistent signals, these are due to the receiver coils EMI resonances.

IV. RESULTS

The high frequency prototype instrument, that is under development at USA army cold region research and engineering laboratory, is depicted on the Figure 2. The system consists a single transmitter loop and figure eight receiver coils. The system operates reliable up to 800 kHz, and yields in phase and quadrature EMI data. Figure 3 shows the comparisons between the model and measured data for the non-metallic 105 mm projectile oriented vertically Figure (3,

top) and horizontally Figure (3, bottom). In the model conductivity of the 105 mm projectile is $\sigma=1.15 \cdot 10^4$ [S/m], which was estimated from the data by minimizing mismatch between the modeled and actual data for both orientations. The results show good agreements between the modeled and actual data for target both orientations for frequency from 5 kHz to 800 kHz. The data above 800 kHz frequencies become unstable. Collected data without target, we found that these instabilities are due to resonance of the receiver coil. In addition the results show that quadrature peaks for both orientations are approximately at 30kHz, thus the existing geophysical time domain EMI systems (such as Metal Mapper, TEMTADS, and etc.), that operate from 40 Hz up to 10 kHz are unable to detect this IEC targets reliable.

V. CONCLUSIONS

Wideband EMI responses are investigated using the method of auxiliary sources. The numerical calculations are validated against measured data obtained by our prototype system. The studies have illustrated that HFEMI sensing technologies can be used for detecting non-metallic subsurface targets, which characteristic EMI signatures occur in the high frequency (>100 kHz) EMI regime. EMI signal analysis also indicate that subsurface target classification algorithms can also extended for non-metallic targets classification.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

This work was supported by the Army Research Office under the project # 55000 –EV.

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